

FORMATION OF GRAMMATICAL SKILLS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: this article talks about the formation of grammatical skills in foreign language teaching, the formation of foreign language teaching skills, and the phenomena of assimilation of grammatical skills to speaking skills are considered.

Key words: polyglossia, teaching a foreign language, grammar, grammatical phenomena, verb, skill, speech, abstract nouns, article, adverb.

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment (in the family, among the public) or in an organized way (in a lesson). Knowledge of language phenomena is studied theoretically. Knowing a language, especially multilingualism (polyglossia), is gaining great importance in our time when international relations are in full swing. When learning any foreign language, the student goes through several stages. Learning the grammar of a foreign language is the most important step. A person who comes across the term "grammar" when reading or listening to someone else's speech can understand it in different ways. There is a reason for this. "Grammar" in the middle school native language course is understood as a field, a branch of linguistics[1]. When studying a foreign language, it is considered the grammatical aspect of speech. Applying the various information described in scientific sources to the purpose of foreign language teaching, the word "grammar" can be limited to two concepts:

- 1) the grammatical side of speech - the grammatical events of the language that occur in speaking, listening, reading and writing (eg, speech pattern; personal form of the verb; article);
- 2) abstract nouns describing linguistic phenomena (e.g. takes the first place in a possessive sentence;
- 3) the singular form of the noun (related to a foreign language) in the plural is added with such and such suffix).

Formation of grammatical skills in foreign language teaching includes several stages. Below we will get acquainted with these parts one by one.

Grammatical events are taught in order to develop spoken grammatical skills. Grammatical material for the formation of skills in the qualification is passed through three stages:

1. The presentation stage consists of introducing a new grammatical unit (presenting it in a speech sample), explaining it when it takes place, and performing the initial grammatical operation.
2. Doing grammar exercises. This stage focuses mainly on skill building.
3. The stage of using a grammatical phenomenon in the types of speech activity.

Grammatical skills are used in the speech, and work is carried out on the transformation of the language into a skill. The first and second stages are a direct grammar training event, the third stage is about both grammatical skills and speaking skills. Pupils get acquainted with the grammatical event presented in the speech sample orally at the lower and middle levels of education, and in writing at the middle and higher levels. Grammatical event is presented in speech pattern, rule style, speech pattern and rule together or as a lexical unit[2]. The list of speech patterns in a foreign language. The rules formalized by linguists and methodologists as appropriate models are known in science under the names rule-

instruction and rule-generalization. A rule-instruction refers to a mental action aimed at using a grammatical phenomenon in speech or recognizing it in reading and listening comprehension. In psycholinguistics, which studies speech issues, this program is called an algorithm. The statement of the rule is a pre-referential basis and is aimed at ensuring the performance of the speech. In other words, the rule can be defined as the theoretical wing of speech practice.

For example, to recognize a determiner, the determined (noun) and the article are taken into account, the determiner comes before or after the noun (depending on the language). A rule generalization is simple theoretical information about the grammatical material studied in a scattered manner in the process of acquiring speech.

A rule should always be concise, well-articulated, goal-oriented, and allow the application or recognition of a grammatical phenomenon.

During the presentation of grammatical material, an inductive or deductive path is followed. During induction, the presentation begins with an example and moves to an abstraction, while in deduction, a rule (or equivalent speech sample) is given, and then examples are practiced. A generalization is issued only if more than one example appears. A single grammatical phenomenon can be studied at the lexical level without rules. A single example is also given lexically in frequently used grammatical events. The presentation stage organizationally includes three consistent methodical activities: introduction (presentation), control of perception and understanding, and preliminary exercises on recognizing and saying a new phenomenon. The introduction is performed as follows. During the development of oral speech, the teacher tells a new event and invites students to imitate [3].

In the next steps, a new event is presented based on a graphical representation. At the same time as saying it, you can write it on the blackboard or students can look

at the graphic representation in the book. In the second part of the introduction, the student's understanding of the phenomenon presented is controlled by the teacher during the speech process. Checking the level of understanding and completing the initial exercises will prepare the ground for the success of moving to the next level. At the beginning of the formation of grammatical skills, it is necessary to emphasize the special importance of performing preliminary exercises, which is the third part. Perception is also the first step in skill formation, in which only the auditory sense/analyzer operates. When imitating, he follows the teacher without the participation of consciousness. As they begin to practice, comprehension begins, and through repetition, speech grammatical automatism is formed. In the third stage, the consistent performance of the initial exercises is the guarantee of strengthening the new phenomenon.

Now the practice period begins so that the presented grammatical events can be turned into skills in a foreign language. First of all, a brief methodological explanation about the skill: grammatical skills mean operations and actions that ensure the correct and automatic use and recognition of morphological-syntactic phenomena in speech. Morphological skills include formation and retention of forms, operations and actions (noun suffixes, verb suffixes, grammatical units used in front of nouns, e.g. articles, prepositions, etc.)[4]. Syntactic skills include word order, word combinations, etc. The ability to use grammatical material includes changing the word and putting the word into the root. During the training phase, tasks related to the correct application of this grammatical skill in a new situation will be completed. (The scope of the concept of a new situation is wide and includes a new task, a new type of activity, acquisition of a new skill/competence, expressing an opinion on a new topic/situation.) Types of tasks are saying and speaking a specific grammatical unit, consists of listening and listening

comprehension, reading and reading comprehension, writing and writing. When we talk about the use of grammar, we understand the use of a certain grammatical event in reproductive speech and recognition in receptive speech, which implies the use and understanding of what is used. In the stage of application, the student uses the grammatical unit to express an opinion and understand the opinion of others.

Full "absorption" of grammatical skills into speech skills is observed. At the proficiency level, the focus is usually on the content of the speech, and language material, including grammar, refers to activities during presentation and practice [4].

In conclusion, it should be noted that the system of teaching the grammar of a foreign language, according to V. S. Setlin's teachings, includes the formation of grammatical skills, the acquisition of grammatical material and the study of generalization. These, in turn, require the performance of exercises aimed at building skills and mastering the material (explanation is focused on understanding and understanding actions). Based on this, we can say that exercises are a means of overcoming difficulties related to material, actions and performances.

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